

Relativistic spotlight

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ABSTRACT

Relativistic motion gives rise to a large number of interesting and sometimes counterintuitive effects. In this work we consider an example of such effects, which we term *relativistic spotlight*. When an isotropic source of soft photons with proper intensity I_0 is placed at rest between a distant observer and photosphere of relativistic wind, its intensity as seen by the observer gets enhanced up to $\sim \Gamma^4 I_0$, where Γ is bulk Lorentz factor of the wind. In addition, these photons may extract a large part of the wind kinetic energy. We speculate that such effect may be relevant for the physics of cosmic Gamma-Ray Bursts.

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Winds of high velocity particles moving outwards from their source are common in astrophysics: the best known example is stellar wind, see e.g. [1]. Winds may exhibit relativistic velocities as in cases of active galactic nuclei [2], gamma ray bursts [3] or pulsars [4].

It is well known that the mean free path of photons in relativistically moving medium is anisotropic, see e.g. [5, §4.9]. For relativistic wind this implies a peculiar shape of the photosphere seen by a distant observer [6]. In particular, a steady spherical wind with constant radial velocity has the photosphere $r = r_{ph}(\theta)$ given by [7,8]

$$r_{ph}(\theta) = \tau_0 R_0 \left(\frac{\theta}{\sin \theta} - \beta \right), \quad (1)$$

where r is radius and θ is the polar angle around the line of sight of the observer, $\tau_0 = \sigma n_0 R_0$, σ is scattering cross section, $n(r) = n_0 (r/R_0)^{-2}$ is the laboratory density of the wind with constant radial velocity $v = \beta c$, c is the speed of light, n_0 is the density at the base of the wind with radius R_0 . The value of radius $R_{ph} = r_{ph}(\theta = 0)$ on the line of sight is referred to as photospheric radius of the wind $R_{ph} = \tau_0 R_0 (1 - \beta) \simeq \tau_0 R_0 / (2\Gamma^2)$, where the last equality holds for large bulk Lorentz factor Γ of the wind, $\Gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2} \gg 1$. In what follows we assume this is always the case.

However, only a small part of the entire photosphere within the relativistic beaming angle $\theta_b = 1/\Gamma$ around the line of sight

has the radius $r_{ph}(\theta) \sim R_{ph}$. For $\theta \gg \theta_b$ the radial coordinate of the photosphere is much larger, $r_{ph}(\theta) \sim \tau_0 R_0 \simeq \Gamma^2 R_{ph}$. Hence the photosphere of the relativistic wind described by Eq. (1) is concave due to a narrow dip along the line of sight. This specific shape of the photosphere plays a crucial role in determination of observational properties of emission originating at the photosphere, see e.g. [9]. In fact, almost all radiation originating from the optically thick region of the wind comes to the observer from the part of the photosphere within the relativistic beaming angle around the line of sight.

In this Letter we discuss another effect of this anisotropy in relativistic wind. Consider an isotropic stationary point source of photons located on the line of sight at the radial position $r = R_*$, see Fig. 1. When such a source is located beyond the photospheric radius of relativistic wind with $R_{ph} \lesssim R_* \lesssim R_{ph} \Gamma^2$ its intensity for a distant observer gets enhanced by a large factor up to Γ^4 . For ultrarelativistic winds occurring e.g. in GRBs the Lorentz factor may be as large as $\sim 10^3$. Consequently, the source of photons may be located far above the photospheric radius, up to $10^6 R_{ph}$, and its intensity may be enhanced up to 10^{12} times! Due to large anisotropy in the mean free path of photons only small fraction of them reaches the observer without any scattering. For all photons emitted beyond some critical angle φ_{max} around the line of sight the wind is opaque. It means that at some point along their trajectories where the optical depth becomes sufficiently large, they start to scatter. This point with coordinates $r = R$, $\theta = \varphi - \alpha$ is shown on Fig. 1. The scattering indicatrix has a preferential direction, which is the radial direction of the wind. Thus an essential part of photons is scattered also towards the observer. The most important aspect here is that for large Γ the drastic compression of the ellipse of the mean free path, shown in Fig. 1 by dashed

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Fig. 1. Geometry of photon scattering. Photons are emitted isotropically from the source at $R_* > R_{ph}$. Most photons emitted at the angle φ with the line of sight are scattered at the distance λ from the source in the point with radial coordinate R . In this point the angle between the direction of photon propagation and the velocity of the wind is α . The photosphere of the wind is shown as thin blue curve. The ellipse of local mean free path, given by Eq. (3) is shown as dotted red curve. The scattering indicatrix is shown by dashed-dotted curve. Observer's detector is located to the right in point O. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

curve, occurs. This effect is accompanied with the compression of the scattering indicatrix. For very large Γ practically all light emitted from the source is channeled towards the observer along its line of sight. Hence the wind plays a role of a reflector which concentrates the scattered emission within a narrow angle with the line of sight.

The large enhancement in intensity as seen by a distant observer is due to two effects: the preferential scattering of photons in radial direction and the increase of photon energy after the scattering by a factor $\sim \Gamma^2$. We will refer to this phenomenon as *relativistic spotlight effect*. In what follows we give a quantitative description of this effect.

Consider photons emitted at angle $\varphi > \varphi_{max}$ from the point source described above, see Fig. 1. The optical depth of the wind between two points with coordinates $(R_*, 0)$ and $(R, \varphi - \alpha(R))$ is given by [8]

$$\tau(R_*, \varphi, R) = \tau_0 \frac{R_0}{R_*} \left[\frac{\varphi - \alpha(R)}{\sin \varphi} - \beta \left(1 - \frac{R_*}{R} \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha(R)$ is the angle between the direction of wind velocity and the direction of photon propagation. The expression (1) is recovered from this formula for $\tau(r_{ph}, \theta, \infty) = 1$. Since $R_* > R_{ph}$ the wind is transparent for small angles $\varphi < \varphi_{max}$, where φ_{max} is determined by the condition $\tau(R_*, \varphi_{max}, \infty) = 1$. Due to strong dependence on φ the wind is opaque for $\varphi > \varphi_{max}$. Moreover, the ratio $\tau(R_*, \varphi \gg \varphi_{max}, \infty) / \tau(R_*, \varphi = 0, \infty)$ is on the order of Γ^2 . Photons with angles $\varphi > \varphi_{max}$ will be scattered for the first time near the point with coordinates defined by equating expression (2) to unity. The distance of this point to the source is approximately given by the local mean free path [6]

$$\lambda(R_*, \varphi) = \frac{1}{\sigma n(R_*)(1 - \beta \cos \varphi)} = \frac{R_*^2}{\tau_0 R_0 (1 - \beta \cos \varphi)}. \quad (3)$$

This equation describes an ellipse with eccentricity β and focus located at the point R_* , see Fig. 1.

Due to relativistic bulk motion of electrons the photons are scattered into the radial direction of the wind motion with $\alpha \lesssim \theta_b$. The scattering indicatrix is shown in Fig. 1 by a dashed-dotted curve. Since the optical depth in this new direction is small most photons will escape after single scattering event.¹ Moreover, the

¹ Indeed, Monte-Carlo simulations show that the average number of photon scatterings is changing from 2 to 0.5 for $R_{ph} \lesssim R_* \lesssim R_{ph} \Gamma^2$ (D. Bégué, private communication).

Fig. 2. Enhancement of the photon number intensity J/J_0 along the line of sight as function of the radial position of the photon source in relativistic steady wind with $\Gamma = 100$. Dashed line shows approximate results obtained by Eq. (4).

Fig. 3. The same as in Fig. 2 for the intensity I/I_0 . Dashed line shows approximate results obtained by Eq. (5).

inverse Compton scattering typically increases the energy of the photon by a factor Γ^2 , providing an effective way to extract the wind energy and momentum. Actually, the interaction between the electron and the photon can be considered as Thomson scattering in the reference frame comoving with the wind, as soon as electrons in the wind have nonrelativistic temperature and initial energy of photons is $\epsilon \lesssim m_e c^2 / \Gamma$, where m_e is electron mass.

For simplicity we assume that photons emitted with angle φ with respect to the line of sight are scattered exactly at the distance λ from the source. The distant observer sees only part of the scattered photons that arrive at the detector, see Fig. 1. The intensity measured by this observer depends on the angular size of the ellipse defined by Eq. (3) as seen from the origin. For $R_* < \Gamma R_{ph}$ the angular size of this ellipse is less than θ_b . In this case photons are scattered in the narrow beam with angular spread θ_b around the line of sight, independently on the position of the source R_* . The larger is the Lorentz factor, the larger is the intensity seen by the distant observer. This is due to the fact, that both ellipses shown in Fig. 1 become highly compressed with increasing Γ . For $R_* > \Gamma R_{ph}$ the angular size of the scattering ellipse exceeds θ_b and the amount of scattered photons reaching the observer is reduced. This is due to the fact that photons are scattered into a wider cone. The intensity seen by the distant observer in this case decreases as R_*^{-2} .

These results are confirmed by integration of photon and energy fluxes towards the observer over the ellipse given by Eq. (3) with the scattering indicatrix which is isotropic in the reference frame comoving with the wind, see Figs. 2 and 3. The analytic expressions are cumbersome, but can be approximated by simple formulae. For $R_* < 2\Gamma^2 R_{ph}$ the enhancement of the photon number intensity is

$$J/J_0 \simeq \frac{8\Gamma^2}{1 + R_*^2 / (2\Gamma^2 R_{ph}^2)}, \quad (4)$$

while the enhancement of intensity is

$$I/I_0 \simeq \frac{16\Gamma^4}{1 + R_*^2 / (2\Gamma^2 R_{ph}^2)}. \quad (5)$$

For $R_* > 2\Gamma^2 R_{ph}$ the spotlight effect is negligible, as at this radius the medium is transparent in almost all directions. The observed intensity enhancement is shown in Figs. 2 and 3 as function of the position R_* of the isotropic source of photons for the bulk Lorentz factor of the wind $\Gamma = 100$. The agreement between analytic results and their approximations (4) and (5) improves for higher Γ .

One may consider an extended stationary isotropic source of photons in the rest frame of the observer with the center located on the line of sight in the same range of radii $R_{ph} \lesssim R_* \lesssim R_{ph} \Gamma^2$. When the transverse size of the source is larger than R_*/Γ the photon flux for a distant observer is equivalent to that of a spherical shell with the radius R_* emitting with the same surface brightness in the absence of the wind. Since most photons are upscattered and their laboratory energy increases by a factor Γ^2 the energy flux is increased by the same factor Γ^2 , compared to the case without the wind.

The enhancement of the intensity is due to the kinetic energy of relativistic wind. It is interesting to note that this kinetic energy can be efficiently extracted by the photons.² One can estimate the luminosity of the stationary spherical source L_* required for deceleration of the wind. The wind is traditionally characterized [10] by its luminosity $L = \Gamma \dot{M} c^2$, where \dot{M} is the rest mass ejection rate. The deceleration of the wind by the spotlight effect changes the form of the photosphere given by Eq. (1), making it less concave. Then for $L_* \gtrsim \dot{M} c^2 / \Gamma$ the kinetic energy of the wind is extracted almost entirely and the relativistic spotlight effect disappears.

The enhancement of intensity of a photon source by a factor $\sim \Gamma^4$ is also known in several different contexts: the reflection off relativistically moving mirror [12, p. 915]; the emission of a source, relativistically moving towards the observer [5, Eq. (4.97)].³ Nevertheless, the spotlight effect cannot be reduced to either of the two: the enhancement of the static source is due to the presence of relativistic medium providing strong anisotropy of the optical depth. In particular, in both above mentioned cases the enhancement of the intensity does not depend on position of the source, unlike the effect considered here, cf. Eq. (5).

This phenomenon may find an application in GRB physics, provided the photon source is located within the relativistic beaming

cone around the line of sight. This requirement is rather natural in relativistic context. The problem of conversion of kinetic energy into radiation is well known. The mechanism described above provides an efficient solution to this problem. In fact, when only a fraction $1/\Gamma^2$ of the kinetic energy of relativistic outflow is converted into soft photons emitted *isotropically* in the rest frame of the observer, such photons will extract large part of the kinetic energy of the outflow. For instance, in the relativistic outflow with $\Gamma \sim 300$ thermal photons with temperature 1 eV will be upscattered to energies ~ 300 keV, typical for GRB spectra.

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² In the model of [11] the propagation of relativistic wind through photon bath was considered. However the estimation of ratio of photons dragged by the wind in transparent region (considered here) is incorrect, since the authors did not take into account the anisotropy of the optical depth properly.

³ We thank the anonymous referee for attracting our attention to this similarity.